

Academic Analysis on Secularism and Its Application in the Republican Era

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Abstract

Although the Republic of Turkey was set up on the ruins of a multi-ethnic and multi-religious empire, a significant homogeneity process was an essential part of the process of constructing the country. This occurred often during the process of nation-building. It is understood that the republican regime has the quality of being a "desirable citizen." Because of this understanding, the republican regime has been subjected to discrimination against certain groups during the process of nation-building, which has resulted in unfavorable outcomes. The Republican regime's conception of who constitutes a "desired citizen" led to the emergence of these unforeseen outcomes because of its policies. At the time when the country was going through the process of being set up, the requirements for citizenship were decided upon and laid down in detail. It is conceivable to codify citizenship in a pragmatic manner based on the needs of modernization if it is regarded as a tool for modernization and country building. This is achievable if citizenship is seen as a tool for modernization and nation building. The behavioral dimension is going to be the first one that is talked about in this section. When there are no major political players working toward the collapse of the democratic government or the effort to forcefully quit the state, one may say that a democracy has been combined. This is one of the conditions that must be met. ("Solved One of the conditions that must be met to apply the - Chegg") When there are no significant political players pushing for the collapse of democratic governance, this outcome is inevitable (Linz and Stepan , 1996: 6). The feelings that are shared by most of the people make up the second dimension. When most people in a society are convinced that democratic institutions and procedures supply the strongest basis for government, it is said to have reached the point where democracy is "the only game in town."

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This is the point at which democracy is said to have reached "the only game in the city." When something like this occurs, people often refer to it as "being the only game in town." (Linz and Stepan , 1996: 6). With the purpose of contributing to the existing body of scholarly work, the current research presents the studies and practices of secularism throughout the Republican Era from a new point of view.

Keywords: *Secularism, Republic of Turkey and Secularism, Secular Practices*

1. Introduction

If citizenship is seen as an instrument for modernization and country development, then this will certainly be the case. One of the possibilities that have been proposed is that this is the case (Burak, 2015: 27). One of the many reasons why the Kemalist elites exploited the civic rule as a tool in their social engineering was because of this. Under the context of the ideology of the state, they even went as far as to degrade people who were considered undesirable. On the other hand, it seems to have conducted everything that it was meant to when democratic consolidation became "the only game in town" (Linz and Stepan , 1996). The consolidation of democratic institutions may be ensured by the operation of these three components. The great leader Atatürk believed that in the system he had set up, it was necessary to eliminate dogmatic and religious influences at all levels in the state. Instead, he believed that it was necessary to create a social model that is logical and rational and progressing under the leadership of science. He concluded that he could put this circumstance into practice, especially with secularism (Yürük, 2005). The growth of the legal infrastructure, namely the constitution, is the primary focus of the third aspect of the consolidation of democratic institutions. When players within the state, both governmental and non-governmental, are subject to rules set for resolving disputes and agree to these rules, democratic consolidation has been accomplished. These rules may also be changed according to the norms that have been established. According to Linz and Stepan (1996: 7), a combined democracy needs five separate regions that interact with one other for such consolidation to occur. This is because such consolidation is necessary for a democracy to exist. For this to take place, democracy has to be created first. If these requirements are not satisfied, it will not be feasible to enhance democracy; rather, it will be necessary to construct democracy from the ground up. The first of these interrelated spheres is that of the civic society. The ability of people, self-organizing organizations and movements,

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as well as journalists, to voice their thoughts makes civil society an essential component. This is because it supplies a venue for them to do so. Considering this fact, civil society becomes an essential component.

2. The Role of Civil Society

The function of civil society is analogous to that of a check or balance on the undemocratic or corrupt elements in society (Linz and Stepan , 1996: 7). The domain of political and social interaction is the second area of connectivity that will be investigated. The explanations offered by Linz and Stepan suggest that the political society acts as a stage upon which power struggles are played out, and that it is upon this stage that the political entity is after constituted. It is the foundation upon which the legal right to control public power is created, and it is the basis of the legal right to control public power. It offers legal protections that are founded on the principle of the rule of law and are administered by a governmental machinery that is free from bias (Linz and Stepan , 1996: 8). The connection between religion and politics in Turkey is in a state of perpetual flux and is susceptible to a broad range of adjustments as a direct consequence of the constantly developing socio-economic backdrop in the country. Yet, secular organizations that embrace and promote secularism like Turkey and religiously sensitive organizations that are sensitive to religion issues sometimes find themselves on different sides of societal conflicts. The trajectory and rate of growth are both subject to the sway of sociopolitical elites and other factors running on a global scale (Yavuz Citation2003; Davison Citation2003; Warhola and Bezci Citation2010). Yet, divides n does not show discrete splits since there are various regions in which the two groups interact and overlap with one another. In some instances, there is some overlap between the two groups, as well as interaction between them (Sakalliolu Citation 1996). Those who consider themselves to be modernist, western, and secular are more likely to have a position that is politically conservative as well as one that is exclusive; this is a differentiation that is exclusive to Turkey. For instance, today, there is a sizable number of people who adhere to cultural conservatism, are sensitive to religious sensitivities, and push for secularism. These people also consider themselves to be sensitive to religious sensitivities. This is a distinction that helps to progress secularism and

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adds to its overall growth. The socioeconomic realities of the nation, which are the result of paradoxical circumstances as well as conundrums, supply the gasoline for the forces that propel Turkey onward, but not in a favorable manner. This is since paradoxical situations are an equally important component of the fabric of the country as dualities. As a result of these factors, the primary emphasis of this special issue is going to be placed on the dynamics of the connection between religion and secularism as led by the AKP. This is since the AKP has held power in Turkey continuously since 2002. This connection is put into perspective in a special edition that investigates the shifting roles that Islam and Turkish secularism play in the world as it exists now. Some people have tried to explain the incident by saying that Mustafa Kemal Atatürk's attitude towards Islam had a role in the early Republican party's march towards secularism. This is one of the explanations that has been proposed. This is one of the ideas that has been proposed by several different scientists. On the other hand, Atatürk's words reveal sentiments toward Islam that are rather conflicting. 11 He has lauded Islam as "the most reasonable and natural of all faiths" in a few of his remarks. In other remarks, however, he is shown as being opposed to religion, particularly in terms of the influence it has on society. For example, he says that "[t]he Republic cannot be the country of sheikhs, dervishes, followers, and sectarians." This may be found in the book 75 Years' Worth of Daily Devotional Teachings, which was released in 1998, on pages 241 and 247. It has been argued that "civilization is the rightest sect because it is the most actual sect." Scholars who tried to grasp Atatürk's perspective of Islam by historicizing and contextualizing Atatürk's views within the framework of the Republic's transition timeline were unable to give any more insight. This was the case even though they attempted to do so. Although there are those who believe that Atatürk always intended to take a "radical" stance towards Islam and that his "moderate" comments from the early years (such as in his call for jihad in the early years) should be taken as a sign of his pragmatism despite the fact that there are those who believe that Atatürk always intended to take a "radical" stance towards Islam. for example, see Tanor 1955:66 and Kili 2003), there are many who argue that the steady hardening of his viewpoint is not the product of grand planning, but rather the consequence of the results of little decisions made over time (see also: Tanor 1955:66 and Kili 2003). (Davison 1998). The scientific explanations that concentrate largely on the reasons why Atatürk turned to secularism are just as confusing as the other hypotheses. Some people believe that the Ottoman experience, which proved that it was difficult to

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modernize the state and society without removing Islam from the dominant set of beliefs, was the driving force behind the development of secularism as a political and social ideology. The Ottoman experience showed that it was difficult to modernize the state and society without removing Islam from the dominant set of beliefs.

3. Secularism in People's Experiences

In the experiences of other individuals, secularism has functioned as a "management method," to use Foucault's terminology; it has aided in restraining the "environment." To put it another way, it tried to keep control of the "center" (Mardin 1977). Although they are distinct from one another, the two narrative sequences have the aim of comprehending the goings-on of the 1920s by looking at them through the prism of the present day. Because of this, they place an excessive amount of significance on the dynamics of the organization's internal environment while neglecting the dynamics of the international environment. As a result, this ends up in the predicament that was just discussed. The primary divergence between the two points of view is that one views Islamic activity as an ongoing danger to secularism, while the other sees it more as a movement that is nearly freeing and is structured to fight measures that would make secularism more prevalent. The leadership of the Republican Party. Both points of view are correct. The prior viewpoint may be summed up in the following way:

Mustafa Kemal, with this aim,

- *-Abolition of the caliphate,*
- *- The Law of Tevhid -i Tedrisat,*
- *- Adoption of the Civil Code,*
- *- Abolition of the Ministry of Sharia and Evkaf ,*
- *- Abolition of Sharia Courts,*
- *He conducted the revolutions that formed the basis of the Republic of Turkey, which included secularism, such as the adoption of the Dress and Hat Law, until 1930 (Yürük, 2005).*

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From the 1930s, the method of realizing revolutions that typically incorporates secularism in social and societal domains has been followed. This method of implementing revolutions has been followed since the 1930s. Mustafa Kemal was the one who really conducted the revolutions that covered the political arenas. Following these revolutions, it was time for the rules that would control social life and bring the Turkish people to a civilized position. These regulations were necessary in order to get Turkey to this stage. In light of this, the 1930s will be remembered in history as the period during which the basis of modern Turkey was formed, an attempt was made to reduce the gap between secular practices and civilized western civilizations, and an effort was made to make up for the lost years (Dac and Dal, 2014).

A separation of religion and state is what is meant by the term secularism. A secular state is a concept that runs under the presumption that the state should not be dominated by the religious beliefs and leaders of a particular religion. The Republic of Turkey was established in 1923, and since then, secularism has been acknowledged and practiced across the country.

The concept of secularism refers to the fact that the government and the state of Republican Turkey have absolutely nothing to do with people's religious views. The state is an entity that protects and delivers services to everyone on an equal basis, regardless of the religious convictions that they may have. This does not make it possible for religious views to dictate the policies of the state, nor does it make it possible for the state to act on religious convictions.

The man responsible for establishing the Republic of Turkey, Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, is highly adamant about the need of secularism, and he has done much research and study on this topic. Atatürk actively promoted secularism as a replacement for the Ottoman Empire's preexisting religious framework and worked to guarantee that the Ottoman state was completely divorced from religious convictions.

The adoption of secularism in Republican Turkey was carried out via the banning of religious rituals, the removal of religious symbols from state institutions and official locations, as well as religious teaching and the closure of religious schools. These studies had the dual objectives of discouraging any involvement on the part of the state in matters of religious belief and developing a framework for the state that would provide equal protection to all citizens.

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4. Conceptual Framework; The Concept of Secularism and Its Historical Development

French is the source of our use of the term "secularism" in our language. Nonetheless, the term has its roots in Greek. The definition of the term "secularism" originates from the Greek words "laikos," which means belonging to the multitude, the people, or the mass, and "laos," which denotes the mass or the community that cannot be a priest. Together, these words form the root of the English word "secular" (Duman, 2010).

When looking at the evolution of secularism on a global scale, the Renaissance and Reformation movements represent the most significant turning points in the development of this concept. The dogmatic constraints that were placed on thinking were alleviated as a result of the developments that took place in the domains of literature and art during the Renaissance. Martin Luther King Jr.'s social reform activities provided the basis for the establishment of a new religious group known as Protestantism, while events such as the seizure of power inside the Christian church opened the way for the development of secularism (Ertan, 2007).

To adhere to the principles of secularism, a state is required to maintain a neutral stance on matters of both religion and the outside world, as well as to respect the religious convictions of its citizens. This idea originated in Europe during the 18th and 19th centuries, and its primary objective was to entirely free the government, particularly in France, from any and all religious influences. The relevance of secularism lies in the fact that people do not discriminate against one another on the basis of their various religious views and that the government respects the religious beliefs of all individuals in an equal manner.

Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, who was instrumental in the establishment of the Turkish Republic, made a point to stress the significance of secularism at this time. Atatürk advocated for the adoption of a secularism principle that should be implemented throughout Turkey's social, cultural, economic, and political spheres, and he initiated a number of revolutionary changes in order to put this concept into practice. These revolutions, which included the adoption of secularism, laid the foundation for what would later become the Republic of Turkey.

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The adoption of secularism in the Republic of Turkey has resulted in the state making a distinct distinction between concerns of religion and those of a secular nature, as well as ensuring that the religious convictions of the population are honored. The adoption of secularism in the Republic of Turkey made it possible for individuals of various religious faiths to coexist peacefully with one another. At the same time, the institutionalization of secularism was crucial in contributing to the maintenance of the Republic of Turkey's social and political equilibrium and stability.

Although there were some regulations pertaining to secularism during the Ottoman period, particularly during the Tanzimat period, secularism was not guaranteed until 1876 with the passing of the "Kanun-u Esasi." This occurred despite the fact that there were some regulations related to secularism during the Ottoman period. Since Article 11 of the Kanun-u Esasi contains declarations that "establishing the freedom of religion in Turkey and the free practice of all faiths in the nation are under the protection of the state." This is the reason why freedom of religion is protected in Turkey. Therefore, the shift to the secularism system was not possible given the constitutionalism that was being used. Because there were still assertions about the caliphate institution that was still active and the state's submission to Islam as a religion (Duman, 2005).

At the period of time when Turkey was in the process of reconstructing the country after its victory in the War of Independence, Turkey focused its attention on the western cultures. Secularism may be seen as the guiding idea behind this attitude. As a result of the fact that Atatürk's objective is to establish a state that is free, national, and secular. In order to accomplish this goal, it is essential that religious influence be eliminated from all organizations run by the state. In addition, Atatürk desired to replace the stereotypical and supernatural thought systems of the time with those of a researcher, scientist, rationalist, and innovator. This was his goal throughout those years (Kara, 2002).

Mustafa Kemal was able to see clearly the advantages that secularism would bring to the newly established Turkish state. As a result, he believed that religion and politics should be kept separate, and that individuals should practice their religion in accordance with their own personal belief systems. Although Mustafa Kemal was contemplating and putting his ideas into

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practice, he also acquired valuable lessons from the difficult times that western nations had through in the past (an, 2012).

5. Free Republic Party

The Free Republican Party was the second opposition party to be established in the Republic of Turkey. It was established on August 12, 1930 at Mustafa Kemal's request and has been led by Fethi Okyar from its inception. The Progressive Republican Party, which had been established in 1924 and had rapidly developed into the central organization for those who opposed the rule, was put out of business. There was never another opposition party created until the year 1930 (an, 2012).

The fiscal crisis that began in the United States of America in 1929 had a profound impact on the rest of the globe, including our nation. As a direct consequence of this circumstance, our nation also experienced a severe economic downturn, which led to a national debt problem. The public became aware of the downturn in the economy, and as a result, the administration received regular criticism on the subject of these difficulties. In point of fact, Mustafa Kemal remarked that, when traveling around the nation, he mostly listened to concerns about these kinds of problems. He was in such a state that he told his general secretary, H. Riza Soyak, the following: "I'm sad, youngster, I'm in severe misery." You need to understand that we take the time to hear out criticisms and complaints everywhere we go. According to Yürük (2005), "every side is in profound poverty, both material and spiritual anguish."

When it comes to the 1930s, there is a fear that the economic crisis would produce a passive impact on the society. This is due to the fact that the Great Depression occurred during this time period. Taner Timur was correct when he said that there were two different paths to choose in the issue. "Either to soften the rule with the restoration of democratic rights and freedoms, or to harden it entirely," was the choice that was presented. In response to this predicament, the first of the two potential solutions that were proposed was chosen to pursue; specifically, efforts to de-escalate the situation were made via the formation of the Free Republican Party. Moreover, Atatürk was quoted as saying, "*The multi-party government is a system that I have been in love with and support ever since I was a teenager.*" I consider this to be one of the

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guiding principles of the republic," he said, highlighting an essential component that is one of the pillars around which democracy is built (Duman, 2010).

Mustafa Kemal asked several of his closest friends to launch the Free Republican Party after all of these events had place, and they did so at his request. In this regard, Mustafa Kemal obtained a favorable reaction from Fethi Okyar, who was the ambassador of Paris. Mustafa Kemal had offered to create an opposition party to Fethi Okyar, and Fethi Okyar had accepted the offer. Hence, in addition to Fethi Bey, Nuri Conker, Ahmet Ağaoğlu, and Mehmet Emin Yurdakul were among the founders of the Free Republican Party. The party's headquarters were established in Istanbul on August 12, 1930 (an, 2002).

6. Menemen Incident

The global economic crisis that began in 1929 expanded to our nation and manifested itself here with more severity, particularly in the areas of the country that were undergoing the process of industrialization at the time. It has been decided to immediately establish the Free Republic Party in order to find a solution to these economic problems, as well as to reduce the tension that has developed as a result of the growing criticism that the general public has directed toward the government as a direct result of the country's financial problems. The policies of the administration came under attack from this second opposition party that was created. Reactionary factions who intended to take advantage of this terrain eventually came out into the open after hiding for some time (Yürük, 2005). This occurred when supporters of the old system began to flood into the party.

The Sheikh Said Rebellion, which took place in 1924 following the foundation of the Progressive Republican Party, which was the first opposition party in the history of the Republic, was destroyed by the army, but the nation entered a period of legal quiet after that. A scenario quite similar to this one occurred in 1930 with the formation of the second opposition party, which was followed by the anti-regime and secularism Menemen Incident (Dac and Dal, 2014).

Towards the dictatorship and the government, the Free Republican Party also roused the religious groups, who had remained silent for a time. This quiet had been caused by the Free Republican Party. Sheikh Assad, the head of the Naqshbandi sect, was the one responsible for planning the event. Sheikh Esad's objective in Manisa is to further combine the standing of his sect. To accomplish this goal, he sent his followers to this area. Derviş Mehmed was one of the men who were subordinate to Sheikh Esad and who organized meetings in Manisa and gathered followers for his sects. He went to the villages in Menemen, made propaganda with the slogan "religion is going hand in hand," and by ensuring that the villagers who joined him were armed, they headed towards Menemen. A large-scale investigation was carried out in order to identify those responsible for these inhumane acts against the reforms of Must In the public and the press, the Turkish Grand National Assembly voiced its strong opposition to the terrible events that took place, and protests against the government's reactionary acts continued for a considerable amount of time with telegrams being received from different regions of the nation (Duman, 2010).

In the aftermath of these anti-secular and reactionary riots, martial rule was set up in and around the Menemen area, and around 2,200 individuals were imprisoned in Menemen, Balakesir, Manisa, and Antalya on suspicion of being connected to the events. Following that, on January 3, 1931, under the direction of Mu'lal Mustafa, the Court of War Courts were founded, and the perpetrators who committed the atrocities were put on trial. At these tribunals, 28 persons were found guilty of crimes worthy of the capital penalty, and on February 3, 1931, they were put to death in Menemen. Because of the trials, it was found out that the Menemen event was related to the Naqshbandi Order in some way. It has been found that Şeyh Hoca Esat, Hoca Saffet, Şeyh Halit, and Şeyh Esat's son Mehmet Ali all had an active part in the planning and fulfillment of the events (Dac and Dal, 2014). Mehmet Ali was the son of Şeyh Esat.

7. Turkishization of the Language of Worship

At the time when Turkey was a republic, Mustafa Kemal was the one who first proposed the idea of Turkishizing the practice of worship. Nonetheless, there were tensions surrounding the Turkishization of the language of religion even before the republic was set up. Regarding this

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matter, an assault using the Tanzimats was carried out during the time of the Ottoman Empire, and II. The declaration of the Constitutional Monarchy, in particular the influence of the Unionist discourses, as well as the problem of the Turkish Qur'an and tafsir are among the significant topics that were addressed during this time (Ertan, 2007) .

On February 21, 1925, the possibility of the Qur'an being written in Turkish was brought up for debate in the Grand National Assembly of Turkey. The Assembly concluded that the Qur'an should be translated into Turkish. By this decision, Professor Dr. Hamdi Yazır authored a tafsir that is comprised of 9 volumes and is titled "Hak Dini Kur'an Dili Yeni Meali Turkish Tafsir." Additionally, Kamil Miras and Ahmet Naim authored a translation of hadith that is formed of 12 volumes and is titled "Sahih-i Buhari Concise Isolation Translation." Hence, Mustafa Kemal's perspectives, as expressed on the 14th of August 1923, were put into action (Ertan, 2007).

In 1928, at a time when significant advances had been made in terms of secularism, the Faculty of Theology at Istanbul University established a commission with the mission of researching and examining the challenges of modernization and reform within Islam, as well as providing fresh recommendations. In the following four topics, this commission has categorized the religious proposals and changes it has proposed:

- *"Form of Worship"*
- *"Language of Worship"*
- *"Worship Quality" and*
- *They made some suggestions under the headings of "The Thought Side of Worship" (Duman, 2010).*

Although while the reading of the adhan in Turkish has been put into reality all around the nation with no issues whatsoever, there have been instances in which the responses have not taken place. The responses of a small number of individuals who were present at Bursa Ulu Mosque on February 1, 1933, in opposition to the Turkish adhan, are the ones that stand out as being the most outstanding. After a brief disagreement between the individuals who were protesting the Turkish Adhan and the muezzin who was there, the individuals described above

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walked to the governor's office and continued their uprising there. After the events of this incident, they were detained (Ertan, 2007).

8. The Process of Turkish Women in Obtaining the Right to Vote and to be elected and the Developments

The Law of Unification of Education, which was first put into action on March 3, 1924, transformed the educational system in Turkey into one that was democratic, secular, unified, and nationalist. They were given the right to marry in the form of polygamy, inherit them in social life, separation, practicing the profession they wanted, and other rights with the implementation of the Civil Code on October 4, 1926. Turkish women were also given the right to practice whatever profession they wanted. According to Dac and Dal (2014), after the introduction of the idea of secularism, Turkish women have now had the chance to express themselves in society in a manner that is seen as more comfortable.

In 1930, Turkey passed a legislation that gave women the ability to run for office, vote, and take part in municipal elections for the first time. This was the first political empowerment law for Turkish women. This right, which has been a long-standing goal of Turkish women's rights activists, is also an unmistakable and significant sign of their presence in society as persons. According to Dac and Dal (2014), Turkish women were granted the opportunity to vote and run for positions on village headmanships and boards of elders as early as 1933.

9. Adoption of the Law of Kisve

Regulations were made about the dress code, and in the continuation of this law, it was decided that people other than clergy could not wear religious clothing with another regulation that came into force in the same year (Yürük, 2005). This law was followed by a decision that people could not wear religious clothing with another regulation that came into force in the same year.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Because of the Dress Act, which went into effect in 1934, certain judgments were taken, such as the fact that only the leaders of the many faiths in the nation were allowed to wear religious clothing, with the following exceptions:

- 1- *No matter what sect or religion they belong to, it is forbidden for the clergy to wear a spiritual guise except for their rituals and temples. The state can allow only one spiritual person from each denomination and religion to wear his spiritual clothes, even outside the rituals and temples.*
- 2- *In our country, when they want to carry clothes specific to communities, societies, clubs, committees and schools, such as sportsmanship and scouting, which are or will be withheld by law, they are free to carry only the clothes that are suitable for certain types with the regulation.*
- 3- *It is forbidden for local and foreign people in our country to wear clothes related to politics, military and militia organizations in foreign countries (Yürük, 2005).*

10. Bektashi Rites

Dervish lodges, zawiyas, and graves were all shut down because of a legislation that went into effect in 1925. Also, the rule forbade the practice of religious groups like sects as well as the religious rites and ceremonies that were associated with these organizations. The Bektashi sect was one of the many religious groups that disappeared during this time (Kara, 2002).

Bektashi Rites was the term that was given to the news articles that were published between 1932 and 1937 in the Izmir press that was analyzed throughout the 1930s. There have been reports of individuals who have been found guilty being sentenced to jail or penalties as a consequence of their trials, particularly in rituals that are regularly experienced in Izmir and the cities that are located in its vicinity. Thus, the activities of the sects were not permitted during the time of Mustafa Kemal as a consequence of this. Notwithstanding this, the sects were able to resume their activities when the multi-party system was implemented (Kara, 2002). This was made possible by the compromises that were made on these matters.

11. Argument

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CURRENT SCIENCE

Since the foundation of the Republic of Turkey, secularism has been one of the most significant guiding principles in both the country's social and political life. Atatürk views secularism as a social and cultural revolution, and he considers it to be one of the Republic of Turkey's most important ideals. To adhere to the principles of secularism, a state is required to maintain a neutral stance on matters of both religion and the outside world, as well as to respect the religious convictions of its citizens. This realization is a guiding concept that ought to be implemented throughout all spheres of activity in the Republic of Turkey, including but not limited to its social, cultural, economic, and political spheres.

During the time of the Republican administration, secularism was acknowledged as a guiding concept that need to be put into practice, and a structure that was in line with this principle was put into place. A significant contribution to the establishment of secularism was made by many pieces of legislation, including the Law of Tevhid I Tedrisat, the Civil Code, the Abolition of Shari'a Courts, and the Law on Clothing and Hats. These rules have the dual purpose of ensuring that the state behaves in a manner that is fully independent of religious views while also respecting the religious convictions of its citizens.

It is because to secularism that individuals of many religious faiths are now able to coexist peacefully in the Republic of Turkey, which has been one of the countries that secularism has helped to flourish and prosper. The adoption of secularism in the Republic of Turkey has been one factor that has contributed to the country's achievement of social and political equilibrium and stability. The maintenance of secularism is necessary to guarantee that the Republic of Turkey will continue to flourish and develop within the context of the same ideals in the years to come.

The Republic of Turkey has made the adoption of secularism a central tenet of its political philosophy. In Turkey, the control of social, political, and legal life is based on the notion of secularism, which has been acknowledged and recognized as a basic value. In this piece of study, both the adoption and implementation of the secularist philosophy in Turkey during the period of the Republican government have been scrutinized.

Throughout the process that led to Turkey's transformation from the Ottoman Empire into a nation-state in its own right, the secularist ideology was formally embraced as a guiding

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CURRENT SCIENCE

principle. The transformation of Turkey into a modern state has been greatly aided by the application of this fundamental idea. The adoption of secularism as a guiding principle has generated debate, particularly due to the fact that this approach is incompatible with the established norms of Islamic states.

The adoption of secularism as Turkey's guiding political, economic, and social ideology in the 20th century had a profound impact on those three pillars of the country's society. The separation of matters pertaining to religion and those of the state is what is meant to be accomplished by adhering to the secularist ideal. This concept has been regarded as one of the most essential elements in Turkey's legal system and the running of the state, and it is considered to be one of the most important principles overall.

There have been several repercussions, most notably in the social life of Turkey, as a result of the application of the idea of secularism. In particular, the idea of secularism played a significant influence in the preservation of women's rights as well as the freedom of religion for groups who are underrepresented in society. The formulation of legislation, the administration of education, and the establishment of the legal order are all examples of the notion of secularism being put into practice.

In spite of this, intrusions to the concept of secularism in Turkey in recent years have led to a rise in the country's social tensions as well as its political disputes. The execution of the notion of secularism was complicated by these initiatives, which generated complications. In recent years, particularly, growing Islamist inclinations have led to a weakening of the idea of secularism as a political ideology. This circumstance has a detrimental effect on the ongoing development of democracy in Turkey.

12. Conclusion

Mustafa Kemal used the concept of secularism as a foundation for both the modernizing of society and the establishment of the nation-state that he founded. Because of this, it has executed revolutions and actions based on secularism from the establishment of the republic until the 1930s, respectively. The declaration of the republic, as well as practices toward

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CURRENT SCIENCE

secularism and secularism throughout the course of the subsequent years, are both topics that are covered in this book.

In general, Mustafa Kemal believed that the most essential factor in the development of society was the adoption of a secular worldview. Particularly during the uprisings of the 1930s, he attempted to adapt the thinking system of the revolutions by attaching weight to the social life arrangements that incorporated secularism. This was especially true during the upheavals of the 1930s. Apart from them, he made it quite apparent that there can be no accommodations made with respect to secularism by battling against the regressive groups that challenge the state rule.

While Mustafa Kemal's ultimate goal was to create a model of a modern nation-state based on the ummah community that was typical of the previous government, he unquestionably behaved in accordance with the principles of secularism in his legal procedures and laws. Mustafa Kemal made an effort to modernize society by basing his reforms on the lifestyle of the people in the society as well as on our own culture. Because modernization cannot occur without first adopting a secular worldview.

Today, the Republic of Turkey is considered an example state among eastern civilizations all over the globe due, without a doubt, to the fact that it is a secular state. This is the single most essential reason for this. In recent years, the people who live in the countries of the Middle East and North Africa have revolted against the dictator regimes that were above them, in order to get their freedom and the understanding of democracy they wanted to have, with the movements called the "Arab Spring." On the other hand, the Republic of Turkey has existed for years as a democracy-ruled and well-founded state under secular conditions thanks to Ghazi Mustafa Kemal Atatürk.

Throughout the time of the Turkish Republic, secularism was widely acknowledged to be one of the most fundamental values of the state. The revolutionary movement that Atatürk was leading at the time accepted the idea of secularism, and it has been in place ever since the founding of the Republic. From the beginning of the Republic, the idea of secularism has been institutionalized as a foundational tenet in the administration of the state, the legal system, and the educational system.

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CURRENT SCIENCE

In the course of this line of inquiry, the practice of secularism throughout the time of the Republican administration was investigated. First, a discussion of the factors that led to the acceptance of the concept of secularism and the reasons for its adoption will follow. Following then, an investigation into the practical implementation of the secularism principle and an examination of the impact that the secularism principle had on the social and political life of Turkey during the time known as the Republican period were carried out.

The findings of the study indicate that throughout the Republican era in Turkey, the concept of secularism was implemented in a significant number of spheres of political and social life in the country. In modern society, the protection of the rights of women and members of minority groups has been significantly aided by the application of the secularist philosophy. The formulation of legislation, the administration of education, and the establishment of the legal order are all examples of areas in which the secularist ideology is put into practice.

Yet, the findings of the study show that the implementation of the idea of secularism is fraught with certain difficulties. Particularly in the most recent years, the intrusions to the idea of secularism that have been taking place have produced societal tensions as well as political disputes. The difficulties that arose throughout the process of putting the idea of secularism into practice had a detrimental effect on the democratic process in Turkey.

For this reason, the upholding and practice of secularism as a concept is an essential part in the democratic transition now taking place in Turkey. To the extent that Turkey is committed to the secularist concept, it will be better able to protect fundamental principles and values such as democracy, human rights, and the rule of law.

13. Resources

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